

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON AQUEOUS STEARIC-ACID SOL. PART I

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The cataphoretic velocities of stearic acid sol particles at the room temperature ($25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$) with different concentrations of *n*-butylguanidine sulphate solution (*n*-BGS) have been determined by using a micro-electrophoretic cell. The change in the velocity at different time intervals has also been noted. The unusual velocity-concentration curve has been explained by assuming that the H^+ ions obtained from the acid dissociation form the outer part of the double layer and that envelopes of water molecules or 'hydrospheres', which restrict the freedom of movement, exist round the colloidal particles.

Iyer *et al* (*Half-yearly J. Mysore Univ.*, 1932, 6, 16, 188) observed that when $AlCl_3$ was rapidly added to a stearic acid sol in slight excess of that required for coagulation, a stable sol of opposite charge resulted, and they suggested the existence of transition layers between the phases, containing both adsorbed H_2O and oriented molecules of the non-aqueous solvent. From a study of the influence of H^+ and OH^- ions on colloidal stearic acid sol (*ibid.*, 1927, 1, 183), Iyer *et al.* further pointed out that its behaviour illustrated the importance of hydration. Achar *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1875) have shown that when a stearic acid sol is treated with a neutral salt, acidity appears in the intermicellar liquid. Their observation suggests displacement by the salt cations of hydrogen ions produced by the ionisation of the surface molecules on the stearic acid particles.

From a recent study on the effect of cationic wetting agents on stearic acid sol, Roy *et al.* (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1955, 37A, B, 4, 254) concluded that the added wetting agents formed a complex with the stearic acid molecules at the surface of the colloidal particles. The present paper deals with the cataphoretic study of stearic acid sol particles with *n*-BGS, with a view to elucidating the structure of the interface.

EXPERIMENTAL

The stearic acid sol was prepared by following a method due to Mukherjee (*J. Mysore Univ.*, 1935, 1C, 983). Stearic acid in alcohol (1 g. in 100 c.c.) was added dropwise to boiling water (400 c.c.). The resulting sol was freed from alcohol by further boiling and then filtered through Whatman No. 33 filter paper so as to avoid larger particles. It was then treated with 2 drops of 0.005*N*-NaOH solution. The sol, thus prepared, was stable for many months and exhibited on shaking a streaky appearance.

n-Butylguanidine sulphate was prepared from *n*-butylamine and dimethylisothiourea sulphate by boiling with 50% aqueous alcohol and was recrystallised as needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 206° . The concentration of the aqueous solution of the sulphate was 4%.

A micro-electrophoretic cell with a cylindrical bore (Mattson's type) was employed in the present investigation. The instrument had the additional advantage of being provided with electrical connections by means of agar bridges. It was fixed to a wooden stand and illuminated by means of a point-o-lite lamp provided with a suitable condensing lens system. The voltage between the two agar bridges was measured using a calibrated voltmeter. Both the corrections due to Buswell and Larson (*J. Phys. Chem.* 1936, **40**, 833) and Henry (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 997) were incorporated with a view to obtaining the most accurate results with the microrophoretic cell.

The sol (10.0 c.c. of 0.00045%) was mixed with 5.0 c.c. of *n*-BGS in a bottle and the mixture was shaken almost uniformly for 1 minute. The sol was then transferred to the cataphoretic cell and the velocity of the particles was measured using direct as well as reverse current. An average value of six readings in each direction was taken. The velocities of the particles were recorded at definite time intervals and also with varying amounts of *n*-BGS.

FIG. 1

The results obtained are represented graphically in Fig. 1. The stearic acid sol in these experiments had a concentration of about 0.0003% while the *n*-BGS concentration varied from 0.1% to 1.3%. The curves exhibit some interesting features.

DISCUSSION

It is seen from Fig. 1 that the velocity of particles first decreases to a minimum at about 0.1 to 0.17% *n*-BGS and then rises up to a maximum at about 0.2 to 0.23%, followed by a gradual decrease.

Similar curves have also been observed with emulsions. While studying the cathoretic velocity of saponin-stabilised emulsions of sodium oleate in the presence of electrolytes, King (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1941, **37**, 174) observed a similar curve on the addition of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$. Size-frequency curves were also of the same type. He suggested that salting of the soap adsorbed at the surface was responsible for this effect. Powny and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1941, **37**, 152; 1937, **33**, 1243; 1940, **36**, 57) in their studies on the action of anionic wetting agents like sodium dodecyl sulphate on negatively charged emulsion (Nujol) obtained charges which were opposite to those mentioned above. They attributed the initial rise of the curve to the adsorption of the single long ions and subsequent fall to secondary adsorption of Na^+ ions. The further slow but definite rise was attributed to the formation of genions among the Na^+ ions.

As has been shown by Kruyt (*Colloid Symposium Monograph*, 1926, **4**, p. 304), the constancy of the dielectric constant of the medium cannot be assumed. In fact, KCl shows a minimum at 4.8 mM/litre.

The results can readily be explained in the light of the improved form of Smoluchowski's equation for large insulating particles. According to Henry (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 1024) and Booth (*ibid.*, p. 958) the velocity under unit potential gradient for large insulating particles is given by

$$\frac{U}{H} = \frac{D \xi}{4\pi\eta} \left[\frac{\mu_0 a}{\mu_0 a + \mu_s} \right]$$

where μ_0 = the specific conductivity of the fluid, μ_s = surface conductivity and a = radius of the particles. On the first addition of *n*-BGS, ξ diminishes appreciably, but the quantity in parenthesis remains almost unaltered (μ_0 remaining unchanged owing to the almost complete adsorption of the added *n*-BGS). Hence, first the value of U/H falls and the curve decreases. With further addition of it, ξ diminishes less rapidly while μ_0 increases, and 'a' may also increase due to partial coagulation. If the increase of $\mu_0 a / (\mu_0 a + \mu_s)$ outweighs the decrease of ξ , then the value of U/H increases and the curve will increase. With the addition of more and more *n*-BGS solution $\mu_0 a / (\mu_0 a + \mu_s)$ becomes almost constant (*i.e.*, unity), and hence, the value of U/H decreases in the same way as ξ decreases.

Another plausible explanation can, however, be given as follows: Assuming that H^+ and Na^+ ions, obtained from the acid dissociation and from NaOH respectively, form the outer part of the double layer and that enclaves of water molecules (hydrospheres), which restrict the freedom of movement, exist round the colloidal particles. On adding *n*-BGS at low concentrations, to start with, those simple guanidine ions, which possess a velocity greater than a critical value, their number being guided by the Maxwell's "Distribution law", dive deep into the double layer through the hydrosphere and form surface complex with the stearic acid molecules at the surface of the particles. Thereby, partial charge neutralisation takes place and the H^+ and Na^+ ions are partially expelled from the outer layer. Consequently, ξ and the thickness of the double layer decrease, resulting in a fall in the velocity. Afterwards the charged guanidine ions displace the water molecules and thus destroy the "hydrosphere". The particles now possess a greater velocity which might partly be due to the dehydration and partly due to the increase in the thickness of the double layer because of the presence of the guanidine ions in the outer layer. At higher concentrations, however, the guanidine ions get themselves adsorbed on the surface complex, and the thickness of the double layer decreases further (Bull and Gortner, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1950, 201A, 40).

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